

EFFECTS OF DIFFERENT THERMO-MECHANICAL REFINING PRESSURE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF MEDIUM DENSITY FIBREBOARD (MDF) MADE FROM KENAF (*Hibiscus cannabinus* L.) CORE

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Abstract

The effects of thermo-mechanical refining conditions on the properties of medium density fibreboard (MDF) made from kenaf (*Hibiscus cannabinus* L.) core were evaluated. Kenaf core chips were refined in a pilot scale MDF plant under different refining conditions; refining pressure of 3, 5, 7 bar, each for 3 and 5 minutes refining time. The resulting fibres were consolidated into 700 kg/m³ density board and bonded with 12% of Urea-Formaldehyde (UF) resin and pressed at 160 kg/cm² for 5 minutes. The water absorption (WA), thickness swelling (TS), modulus of rupture (MOR), modulus of elasticity (MOE) and internal bonding (IB) were determined based on MS Standards 1787: 2005. The results indicated that refining pressure has a more dominant effect on the board properties. Refining time however has no apparent effect on the MDF properties. Using lower pressure refining produced board with high WA, TS, MOR and MOE but low IB value. On the other hand, high pressure produced board with low WA and TS but high MOR, MOE and IB. At 7 bar and 5 minutes refining, the MDF recorded WA of 14.6%, TS of 63.2%, MOR of 30.3 MPa, MOE of 3619 MPa and IB of 0.66 MPa.

Keywords: *Refining, Pressure, Time, Physical Properties, Mechanical Properties.*

1 Introduction

Kenaf (*Hibiscus cannabinus* L.) is a relatively new alternative lignocellulosic material for panel manufacture such as particleboard and MDF. Kenaf whole stem comprises of two major parts that are distinctly different; the woody inner core and fibrous outer bark. These two parts of fiber are greatly

different in fibre morphology and chemical composition [1]. The bast is about 40% and the core is about 60% from the total weight of the stem. Fibres from the bast are about 3.6 mm long, and those from the core are 1.1 mm long [2]. The core is light and porous compared to the bast, with a bulk density of 0.10 – 0.20 g/cm³. Between the two types of fibres, core has been reported to have much better bonding ability [3]. Refining is an important process in MDF manufacture. Refining refers to the process of repeated compression and relaxation of plant materials and fibers in water which are provided by the bars and grooves of the refiner disc. In MDF industry, thermo-mechanical pulping (TMP) process is the refining process that augmented by pressure and temperature [4]. Some researchers stated that the thermo-mechanical refining conditions affect the properties of MDF. During refining process, pressure is an extremely important rule in the quality of fibres and dominates the performance of final composites [5]. By increasing the refining pressure and time, the fiber length is reduced and the percentage of broken fibre increased consequently [6] and also reduced the strength of the board [7]. The fine fibers produced when refined at high pressure decrease the stiffness, strength and IB strength of MDF [8]. The objective of this paper is to determine the effect of refining pressure and time on the physical and mechanical properties of MDF made from kenaf core fibres.

2 Material and Methods

2.1 Raw Material Preparation

The main material used in this study was kenaf core which was obtained from National Kenaf and Tobacco Board Kelantan. The core is in chips form and it is about 50-80 mm long and 10-20 mm in diameter. The core chips were refined using

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Thermo-Mechanical Pulping (TMP) at Malaysian Palm Oil Board (MPOB) that equipped with a 30 cm diameter refiner disc, powered by a motor with variable speeds that can reach up to 5000 rpm. The core chips were refined at three refining pressures; 3, 5 and 7 bar for 3 and 5 minutes refining time. Fibres were then dried in the oven to achieve the moisture content (MC) of 4-5%.

2.2 Board Manufacture

The dimensions of boards were 300 x 300 mm with 10 mm of thickness. Target density of the board was 700 kg/m³. The adhesive used was urea formaldehyde (UF) supplied by Malaysian Adhesive Chemical (MAC). The fibres were blended with 12% of UF with 65% solid content. After that, the fibres were collected and hand-formed into homogeneous single-layered mat followed by pre-pressed and consequently pressed in a hot press machine at 175°C for 5 minutes with pressure of 160 kg/cm². Four panels were made for each refining condition with a total of 24 MDF panels.

2.3 Board Evaluation

Prior to the testing, the boards were conditioned at 23 ± 2°C with a relative humidity of 65 ± 2% for about one week until the panels reached equilibrium moisture content. The boards were cut into test specimens according to the Malaysian Standard 1787:2005 [9]. The properties of the MDF were evaluated for its physical properties; water absorption (WA) and thickness swelling (TS), and mechanical properties; modulus of rupture (MOR), modulus of elasticity (MOE) and internal bonding (IB). Four test specimens with 50 x 50 mm in size were prepared from each board sample for WA and TS test for 24 h water immersion. Static bending test was conducted on four 200 x 50 mm specimens using a three-point bending test over a span of 200 mm at a loading speed of 10 mm/min. Four specimens of 50 x 50 mm in size were prepared for IB test. The samples were bonded to the metal blocks with a hot melt adhesive. All samples were tested at a crosshead speed of 0.7 mm/min.

2.4 Statistical Analysis

The data were statistically analyzed using Statistical Analysis System (SAS) software. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to examine the effects of refining condition on the board properties. Least

Significant Difference (LSD) method was used for mean separation to further evaluate the effects of refining pressure and time, and also the interaction between both effects.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Analysis of Variance

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was evaluated for both the physical and mechanical properties. Table 1 shows that there are significant variations in the interaction of pressure and time on the TS (at $p \leq 0.05$). The refining pressures have significant effects on all the MDF properties at $p \leq 0.01$. The refining time has no effect on the MDF properties. The results of statistical analysis of physical (TS and WA) and mechanical (MOR, MOE and IB) properties of MDF are shown in Table 2.

3.2 Mechanical Properties

The MOR and MOE values decreased significantly when the refining pressure was increased from 3 to 5 bar. Refining at pressure 3 bar for 3 min, the MOR and MOE of the boards were 32.6 MPa and 3735 MPa respectively. Both properties were, however reduced to 31.1 MPa and 3386 MPa when the refining time has increased to 5 min. At more severe refining conditions, the MOR obtained were only 24.8 MPa and 25.0 MPa, and MOE of 2669 MPa and 3017 MPa respectively for 5 bar/3 minutes and 5 bar/5 minutes. Apparently, higher degree of hydrolysis had occurred at high pressure refining, causing a reduction in the fiber strength, thus resulted in the low MOR value [10]. Nevertheless, at 7 bar of refining pressure, the MOR and MOE of the boards were increased as longer refining time was applied. This maybe attributed to the production of excessive fine fibers which consequently make the mat easily compressed thus gave better compaction.

3.3 Internal Bonding Strength

The IB values increased with the increasing of refining pressure and time, but decreased with a further increased in refining pressure and prolong of refining time. Board from the mild refining pressure (3 bar) showed lower IB value of 0.52 MPa at 3 minutes and 0.46 MPa at 5 minutes. The board with 5 bar recorded an IB value of 0.67 MPa and 0.66 MPa for 3 and 5 minutes respectively. Severe refining pressure (7 bar) resulted in fine fibers and

caused increase in the bonding area thus improved the IB. When the refining pressure increased, more fine fibres were produced and resulted in increasing of IB values [11]. In addition, during refining, the core is subjected to the steam which might cause thermo decomposition and hydrolyzation of the hemicelluloses components. The steam converts and transforms the hydrolyzed hemicelluloses low molecular weight water-soluble carbohydrates which can act as resin adhesives for bonding [12]. At higher refining pressure, however the IB value decreased. For instance at 7 bar, the IB value of the board decreased to about 0.6 MPa.

3.4 Dimensional Stability

MDF from severe refining conditions showed low TS after 24 hours of immersion in the water. The board made at pressure 7 bar of refining pressure recorded the lowest TS of only 15.4% and 14.6% for 3 and 5 minutes respectively. When the fibre exposed too long under heat, the surface becomes inactive resulted in higher dimensional stability as the fibers lost elasticity through destruction of the aromatic nuclei of lignin [13]. Similar to the trend of TS, the WA of the boards decreased with increasing the refining pressure and time. Boards with refining condition of 7 bar has WA of 68.5% and 63.2% for 3 and 5 minutes. This is most probably due to the increasing the cellulose crystallinity [14] and reduction of the amorphous region in the cellulose, where less OH groups are free in the cellulose and produced more stable board.

4 Conclusion

This study showed that MDF can be manufactured from kenaf core fibre. The refining condition apparently affects the final board properties. Refining pressure has a great effect on the board properties compared to the refining time. Mild refining condition produced boards with high bending strength, but lower IB and dimensional stability. Severe refining condition produced boards with higher IB and dimensional stability, but lower bending strength. The refining condition is crucial in order to obtained better properties of MDF. The fiber refined under 7 bar of refining pressure with 5 minutes refining time showed better mechanical and dimensional properties with WA of 14.6%, TS of 63.2%, MOR of 30.33 MPa, MOE of 3619 MPa and IB of 0.66MPa.

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Table

Effects	WA	TS	MOR	MOE	IB
Pressure	***	***	***	***	***
Time	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Pressure x Time	ns	**	ns	*	ns

Tab. 1 ANOVA for refining conditions of kenaf core.
 ***: Significantly different at $p \leq 0.01$,
 **: Significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$,
 *: Significantly different at $p \leq 0.10$,
 ns: not significant

Refining Pressure (Bar)	Refining Time (min)	Thickness Swelling 24 h	Water Absorption 24 h	Modulus of Rupture (MPa)	Modulus of Elasticity (MPa)	Internal Bonding (MPa)
3	3	21.0 ^a	91.5 ^a	32.6 ^a	3735 ^a	0.52 ^b
	5	19.4 ^b	86.6 ^a	31.1 ^a	3386 ^b	0.46 ^b
5	3	18.3 ^b	74.6 ^b	24.8 ^c	2669 ^d	0.75 ^a
	5	17.3 ^c	73.6 ^b	25.0 ^c	3017 ^c	0.68 ^a
7	3	15.4 ^d	68.5 ^c	28.0 ^b	3379 ^b	0.67 ^a
	5	14.6 ^d	63.2 ^c	30.3 ^a	3619 ^a	0.66 ^a

Tab. 2 Mean value of physical and mechanical properties of MDF from various refining conditions. Values in parentheses are standard deviations. Mean with the same letters in each columns indicate there is no statistical difference at $p > 0.05$.